

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 88

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 88

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 88:0 A Song. A Psalm of the sons of Korah. For the choir director; according to Mahalath Leannoth. A †Maskil of Heman °the Ezrahite.</p> <p>Psa. 88:1 O LORD, the “God of my salvation, I have ^bcried out by day and in the night before You. ² Let my prayer ^acome before You; ^bIncline Your ear to my cry! ³ For my ^asoul has ¹had enough troubles, And ^bmy life has drawn near to ²Sheol. ⁴ I am reckoned among those who ^ago down to the pit; I have become like a man ^bwithout strength, ⁵ ¹Forsaken ^aamong the dead, Like the slain who lie in the grave, Whom You remember no more, And they are ^bcut off from Your hand. ⁶ You have put me in ^athe lowest pit, In ^bdark places, in the ^cdepths. ⁷ Your wrath ^ahas rested upon me, And You have afflicted me with ^ball Your waves. ¹Selah. ⁸ You have removed ^amy acquaintances far from me; You have made me an ^{1b}object of loathing to them; I am ^ashut up and cannot go out.</p>	<p>Psa. 88:1 שִׁיר מִזְמוֹר לְבְנֵי קֹרַח לְמִנְצַחַת עַל-מַחְלַת לְעֵנוֹת מְשָׁכִיל לְהִימָן הָאֶזְרָחִי : ² יְהוָה אֱלֹהֵי יְשׁוּעָתִי יוֹם-צָעַקְתִּי בַלַּיְלָה נִגְדָה : ³ תָּבוֹא לִפְנֵיךָ תְּפִלָּתִי הַטָּה-אָזְנֶךָ לְרִנָּתִי : ⁴ כִּי-שָׁבַעַה בְּרָעוֹת נַפְשִׁי וַחַיִּי לְשָׂאוֹל הִגִּיעוּ : ⁵ נָחַשְׁבַּתִּי עִם-יְזוּרְדֵי בּוֹר הָיִיתִי כַגִּבֹר אֵין אֵיל : ⁶ בַּמַּתִּים תָּכַפְשִׁי כְמוֹ תַלְלִים שֹׁכְבִי קִבֹר אֲשֶׁר לֹא זְכַרְתָּם עוֹד וְהִפַּחַת מִיַּדְךָ נִגְזַרוּ : ⁷ שָׁתַנִּי בְּבוֹר תַּחְתִּיּוֹת בַּמַּחְשָׁכִים בַּמְצֻלוֹת : ⁸ עָלַי סָמְכָה חַמָּתְךָ וְכָל-מְשַׁבְּרֵיךָ עֲנִיתָ סֵלָה : ⁹ הִרְחַקְתָּ מִיַּדְעִי כִמְנִי שָׁתַנִּי תוֹעֵבוֹת לָמוּ כָּלֹא וְלֹא אֲצִיא : ¹⁰ עֵינַי דָּאֲבָה מֵי עֵנִי קָרַאתִיךָ יְהוָה בְּכָל-יוֹם שִׁטְחִתִּי אֵלֶיךָ כַפִּי : ¹¹ תַּלְמִתִּים תַּעֲשֶׂה-בִּלְאֵי אֵם-אֶרְכָּאִים יִקְוֹמוּ אִיזְדוּךָ סֵלָה : ¹² הִיִּסְפַר בְּקִבֹר תִּסְדָּךָ אֲמוֹנַתְךָ בְּאֲבִדוֹן : ¹³ הִזְדַּעַע בְּחֹשֶׁךְ בְּלֹא אֵד וְצַדִּיקְתְּךָ בְּאֶרֶץ נְשִׁיחָה : ¹⁴ וְאֲנִי אֵלֶיךָ יְהוָה שׁוֹעֵתִי וּבִבְקָר תְּפִלָּתִי תִקְדָּמְךָ : ¹⁵ לָמָּה יְהוָה</p>

⁹ My ^aeye has wasted away because of affliction;

I have ^bcalled upon You every day, O LORD;

I have ^cspread out my ¹hands to You.

Psa. 88:10 Will You perform wonders for the dead?

Will ^athe ¹departed spirits rise *and* praise You? Selah.

¹¹ Will Your lovingkindness be declared in the grave,

Your faithfulness in ¹Abaddon?

¹² Will Your wonders be made known in the ^adarkness?

And Your ¹righteousness in the land of forgetfulness?

Psa. 88:13 But I, O LORD, have cried out ^ato You for help,

And ^bin the morning my prayer comes before You.

¹⁴ O LORD, why ^ado You reject my soul?

Why do You ^bhide Your face from me?

¹⁵ I was afflicted and ^aabout to die from my youth on;

I suffer ^bYour terrors; I am ¹overcome.

¹⁶ Your ^aburning anger has passed over me;

Your terrors have ^{1b}destroyed me.

¹⁷ They have ^asurrounded me ^blike water all day long;

They have ^cencompassed me altogether.

¹⁸ You have removed ^alover and friend far from me;

My acquaintances are *in* darkness.

תִּזְנַח נַפְשִׁי תִסְתִּיר פְּנֵיךָ מִמֶּנִּי : ¹⁶

עֵינַי אֲנִי וְגִזְעַ מִזַּעַר נִשְׁאַתִּי אֲמִיד

אֲפוּנָה : ¹⁷ עָלַי עָבְרוּ חֲרוּנֶיךָ

בְּעוֹתֶיךָ צְמַתוֹתַי : ¹⁸ סָבוּנִי כַפַּיִם

כָּל־הַיּוֹם הִקִּיפוּ עָלַי יָחַד : ¹⁹

הִרְתַּקְתָּ מִמֶּנִּי אֶת־בַּיִת וְרַע מִיָּדַעַי

מִחֲשָׁךְ :

References

Psalm 88:0

[†]Possibly, *Contemplative*, or *Didactic*, or *Skillful Psalm*

[°]1 Kin 4:31; 1 Chr 2:6; Ps 89: title

Psalm 88:1

^aPs 24:5; 27:9

^bPs 22:2; 86:3; Luke 18:7

Psalm 88:2

^aPs 18:6

^bPs 31:2; 86:1

Psalm 88:3

¹Or *been satisfied with*

²I.e. the nether world

^aPs 107:26

^bPs 107:18; 116:3

Psalm 88:4

^aPs 28:1; 143:7

^bJob 29:12; Ps 22:11

Psalm 88:5

¹Lit *A freed one among the dead*

^aPs 31:12

^bPs 31:22; Is 53:8

Psalm 88:6

^aPs 86:13; Lam 3:55

^bPs 143:3

^cPs 69:15

Psalm 88:7

¹*Selah* may mean: *Pause*, *Crescendo* or *Musical interlude*

^aPs 32:4; 39:10

^bPs 42:7

Psalm 88:8

¹Lit *abomination to them*

^aJob 19:13, 19; Ps 31:11; 142:4

^bJob 30:10

^cPs 142:7; Jer 32:2; 36:5

Psalm 88:9

¹Lit *palms*

^aPs 6:7; 31:9

^bPs 22:2; 86:3

^cJob 11:13; Ps 143:6

Psalm 88:10

¹Or *ghosts, shades*

^aPs 6:5; 30:9

Psalm 88:11

¹I.e. place of destruction

Psalm 88:12

¹I.e. faithfulness to His gracious promises

^aJob 10:21; Ps 88:6

Psalm 88:13

^aPs 30:2

^bPs 5:3; 119:147

Psalm 88:14

^aPs 43:2; 44:9

^bJob 13:24; Ps 13:1; 44:24

Psalm 88:15

¹Or *embarrassed*

^aProv 24:11

^bJob 6:4; 31:23

Psalm 88:16

¹Or *silenced*

^{a2} Chr 28:11; Is 13:13; Lam 1:12

^bLam 3:54; Ezek 37:11

Psalm 88:17

^aPs 118:10-12

^bPs 124:4

Ps 17:11; 22:12, 16

Psalm 88:18

^cJob 19:13; Ps 88:8; 31:11; 38:11

Targum

Psa. 88:1 A song and a psalm composed by the sons of Korah, with a prayer; for praise; a good lesson composed by Heman the native. ² O LORD God my redemption, daily I have made complaint; in the night my prayer is before you. ³ May my prayer come before you; incline your ear to my plea. [ANOTHER TARGUM: Let my prayer for your people, the house of Israel, come before you; and incline your ear to my psalm that I have sung for your glory.] ⁴ For my soul has had its fill of evils; and my life has arrived at Sheol. ⁵ I am reckoned with those who go down to the prison-house; I have become like a son of man who has no strength. ⁶ Like the wicked who died and did not return, having been made free from strife; like those slain by the sword, lying in the grave, whom you no longer remember, since they have been separated from the face of your presence. ⁷ You have placed me in exile, which is likened to the lower pit, among the oppressed in the depths. ⁸ Your fury rests on me, and all evil decrees have broken me; you have afflicted me forever. ⁹ You have removed those who know me far from me; you have made me loathsome to them; enclosed in prison, and I may not go out. ¹⁰ My eye has flowed with tears because of affliction; every day I have called to you, O LORD; I have spread my hands to you in prayer. ¹¹ Could it be that you would work miracles for the dead? Or will bodies that have decayed in dust arise [and] give thanks in your presence forever? ¹² Could it be that your goodness will be talked of in the grave? Your truth in the place of perdition? ¹³ Could it be that your wonders will be known in the darkness of Gehenna? And your generosity in the land of thirst and desolation? ¹⁴ But I have prayed in your presence, O LORD; and in the morning my prayer will come before you. ¹⁵ Why, O LORD, have you forsaken my soul, why will you hide your face from me, that I may not see illumination by your light? ¹⁶ I am afflicted and frail from childhood; I have borne the fear of you, loaded upon me. ¹⁷ Your anger has passed over me; your terrors have destroyed me. ¹⁸ They have surrounded me like water all day; they have encompassed me together. ¹⁹ You have removed friend and fellow far from me; as for those who know me, I am lowly in their mouth.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

It was believed by the people in exile that their situation was divinely ordained to spur Israel's spiritual development. The insecure Jews at that time had to learn to turn to the LORD for strength to find security and a purpose for their lives. The Psalmist adds that the Torah is home and that home is not a particular parcel of land. Another view is that people need to learn to place their lives in the hands of the LORD by living by the Torah. Materialism is not going to save the soul.

Superscript

Heiman was one of Korach's outstanding sons.

A psalm-song by the sons of Korach. To the Sefirah Netzach, who offers victory over a crushing pain, an instruction by Heiman the Ezrachi.

Verses 3 & 4

In exile, the people were beaten down because they could not worship the LORD as they did when the Temple stood in Jerusalem. They felt that their strength to continue was just about gone. They believed that they were disconnected from the LORD. Therefore, they cried out to the LORD to save them from the torture of separation.

For though my soul is sated with troubles, and my life has arrived at the grave.

If I am counted with them that are destined to go down into the grave if I have become as a man bereft of all strength,

Verse seven

Nevertheless Your wrath has clung fast to me, and You have taken the final strength from your billows. Meditate on this verse.

Verse ten

Do you work wonders for the dead, do the departed arise and render you homage? Meditate on this verse.

Notes on this Psalm

The Psalmist seems to be equating the troubles of Israel to that of a dead nation. The belief was that Sheol (Hell) was separate from the LORD. The LORD did not have jurisdiction in Sheol. Therefore, if one was sent to Sheol, that soul would be completely disconnected from the LORD. That was an unacceptable situation for the Hebrew people. The Exile in Babylon felt like being in Sheol.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

